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Role of Yogic Practices on Self-confidence of School Level Boxer's

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of yogic practices on self-confidence of school level boxer. To attain this purpose were randomly selected 50 male boxers students have ranged 13 to 16 years as subject from Saraswati Vidhya Mandir, Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh. The subjects were divided randomly into two groups of 25 each the groups were identified as control group and experimental group. A yoga training program for 3 months was prepared for the experimental group with the advice of a yoga expert. The researcher gave yoga training to the experimental group in the morning for 3 months (5 days a week). All related information was provided to the experimental group before training. The control group did not undergo any type of special training other than their daily routine activities. Self-Confidence was measured by Self-Confidence Scale (Dr. D.N. Sansanwal and Dr. Samita Bhawalkar) 2011. The data were collected from the both groups before and after the training. The experiment was statistically analyzed by using paired sample t-test. The result of this study revealed that the experimental group shows more significant improvement in self-confidence as compared with control group.

Keywords Yogic practices, Self-confidence, Boxer.

Introduction

Yoga originated in India several thousand years ago and today Yoga is spread in all the countries of the world. People have understood the importance of Yoga and have adopted it in their daily routine. Yoga has been beneficial for the welfare of human life since ancient times. Yoga is very important in making man physically and mentally strong and powerful. Through yoga practice man plays a very important role in mental development like self-confidence, decrease in stress, anxiety and depression etc. It is very important for a player to have self-confidence in sports. Boxing is very popular and famous sport all over the world. Boxing is a combat sport. It has been played since the time of the ancient Olympics. Like all the sports, in boxing too it is very important for the player to have self-confidence.

Self-confidence has always been the core of self-development; the building block on which goal setting, motivation, problem solving, communication, willpower and other aspects of self help stem from. No confidence puts us at a major disadvantage in life.

Objective of study

The objective of this study was to investigate the effect of yogic practices on self-confidence among school level boxer.

Review of Literature

Self-confidence is an attitude about your skills and capacities. It means that you accept and trust yourself and have a sense of control in your life. You are aware of your strengths and weaknesses well, and have a positive view of yourself. You set realistic expectations and goals, communicate assertively, and can handle criticism. (University Of South Florida)

Many studies have tried to determine the effectiveness of yoga on athlete self-confidence level. Mr. Rajesh Gaddam et al (2010) found in their study that the yogic practices

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significantly improvement on self-confidence of athletes. O. Gnana Suganthi et al (2016), K. Jaychandran(2014), K. Saravana Kumar et al (2015), and Kapil Dev (2020). These studies also support the intervention of yoga to improve self-confidence and their factors.

S.Kannadasan (2020) conduct a study was to find out the Role of Yoga and Pranayama on Self-confidence, Attitude and Aptitude of the Degree College Students. Researcher finds out the significant effect of yoga and pranayama in enhancing the self-confidence, attitude and aptitude of the degree college students.

Methodology

Methodology: This study was formulated as a random group design, consisting of a pre-test and post-test. Researcher randomly selected 50 male boxers students of ranged 13 to 16 years of the entire population of study carried out on subject randomly assigned to experimental group and the control group. All Subjects were divided into two groups out of them one is experimental group of 25 male subjects and other is control group of 25 male subjects. The self-confidence was measured by self-confidence scale (Dr. D.N. Sansanwal and Dr. Samita Bhawalkar) 2011. The paired sample t-test was used to determine the differences among the pre and post-test means for the data pertaining to the variable in this study. The level of significance was set at 0.05.

Training Program: Experimental Group subjects were given selected yogic practices. They performed specific asanas, pranayama, kriya and Yoga Nidra as scheduled. Relaxation asanas (Shavasana & Makarasana) were performed in supine and prone position after complete each asana. The experimental group has been given three months of yogic practices on a daily basis in morning time 5 days in a week, including Yogasanas, pranayama, kriya and yoga Nidra at Saraswati Vidhya Mandir, Aligarh U.P. Control group was firmly under control without any special training. The control group did not join in any training program, except for their regular daily routine practice and physical education classes.

Statistical Analysis: Paired sample t-test was applied to investigate self-confidence of experimental group subjects and control group subjects.

Analysis

Table 1: Comparison of mean between pre and post-test of control group of self-confidence

Data	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Error Mean	Difference	T	P
Pre	25	55.40	6.506	1.301	1.840	2.185	0.039
Post		57.24	5.118	1.024			

(Tabulated t-value = 2.064, Level of significance = 0.05, df = 24)

Interpretation: The table I shows that there is a statistically significant difference between the "Pre-test" and "Post-test" of control group of self-confidence, with p-value of 0.039 which is less than 0.05 level of significance. Self-confidence was shown slight improvement.

Table 2: Comparison of mean between pre and post-test of experimental group of self-confidence

Data	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Mean Difference	t	P
Pre	25	54.36	8.015	1.603	4.64	4.558	0.000
Post		59.00	5.212	1.042			

(Tabulated t-value = 2.064, Level of significance = 0.05, df=24)

Interpretation: The table 2 shows that there is a statistically significant difference between the "Pre-test" and "Post-test" experimental group of self-confidence, with a p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05 level of significance. Self-confidence was shown good improvement.

Means

Graph 1: Graphical -representation of Self-confidence Mean in Control and Experimental Group in Pre and Post-test.

Findings

The present study was completed done to find out the effect of yogic practices on self-confidence of school level boxers ranged 13 to 16 years old. There are many reasons for low self-confidence in a person, which include fear of failure, social comparison, social economical, anxiety, stress, depression, instability etc. It has been found in many research studies that daily practice of asana, pranayam and kriya has reduced the level of these factors and increased self-confidence. **O.Gnana Suganthi et al (2016)**, **K. Jayachandran (2014)**, **Abhishek K Bhardwaj et al (2015)**. All these studies found out the interference of yoga reduces stress, anxiety, and increase the level of self-confidence.

Let's explain this what the role of yoga in improving self-confidence of school level boxers According to Hatha Yoga Pradipika, in chapter 2, verse 2, it says that

चले वाते चलं चित्तं निश्चले निश्चलं भवेत् ।
योगी स्थाणुत्वमाप्नोति ततो वायुं निरोधयेत्

The body remains unstable as long as breathing continues and air moves in and out of the body. However, the activity of the mind stops and becomes still when the breath is stopped or held. By practicing Pranayama, an individual can master the art of achieving deep concentration and attention of the mind. When the mind and pran align harmoniously, it is termed as Manoyog, leading to a remarkable enhancement in self-confidence.

The improvement of performance in self-confidence is fundamentally linked to the effortless execution of asanas through passive stretching. This approach allows for the easy and comfortable maintenance of final postures, resulting in the smooth and pleasant stretching of various muscles, tendons, and joints. This practice not only fosters internal awareness but also calms the mind and conditions it by engaging the postural reflex axis involving the cerebellum and hypothalamus during asana practice. The activities of both the sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous systems are balanced. Consequently, the body communicates with the mind through various sensations related to position, movement, and balance via interceptors such as muscle spindles and tendons. As a direct result, inner awareness increases, through which self-confidence increases, and the mind attain peace.

Conclusion The results of the present study show a significant mean difference between the pre and post test scores of the experimental group which is caused by the yogic intervention. This indicates that the mean post test score has increased after the delivery of the intervention in our experimental group as compared to the control group and this score is statistically significant. The findings show that our experimental group has a significant increase in confidence before and after the test as compared to the control group. The paired sample t-test statistics indicate that the pre and post test of the control group was marginally significant.

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